

Optimal Capacitor Placement and Sizing in lower Distribution Systems for harmonic reduction and improving voltage profile and Using Particle Swarm Optimization

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Abstract- Electrical distribution system suffers from various problems like reactive power burden, unbalanced loading, voltage regulation and harmonic distortion. Capacitors are very important for improvement of power factor and reducing network losses in the power systems. In recent years, the problem has been reformulated to account for the discrete nature of capacitor sizes and location. As the electrical loads are growing, the distribution system is developing to supply the customers with higher levels of demand. Growing the loads increases the lines current leading to the increase of loss. This also decreases the voltage level in the distribution network. Capacitors are used commonly to solve these difficulties. However, the investment cost is an issue which prevents their wide use. This highlights the importance of optimal allocation and sizing of the capacitors (OASC). This paper proposes to solve the problem using particle swarm optimization (PSO). The findings clearly demonstrate the necessity of reduction harmonics in optimal capacitor placement and sizing to avoid any possible problems associated with adding or capacitors in a power system network. This paper is divided into 2 cases 1 capacitor and 3 capacitor placements. And coding is done using MATLAB software.

Key Words- Shunt capacitors, distribution systems, harmonic distortion, optimal allocation and sizing of the capacitors, particle swarm optimization.

1. INTRODUCTION

Electrical distribution networks are interconnected and meshed networks. They are arranged to be radial in operation. Radial

distributions system is popular because of low cost and simple design. In distribution systems, the voltages at buses reduces when moved away from the substation, also the losses are high. The reason for decrease in voltage and high losses is the insufficient amount of reactive power. The use of shunt capacitors in [1]. The purpose of capacitor placement planning is to define capacitor types, sizes, locations and control schemes for a period that can vary from one to ten years looking for minimizing investment and energy loss costs. Unfortunately, the solution of this problem is difficult to find because of the combinatorial and multimodal characteristics coming from the classic formulation of the problem.

Capacitor Placement in Distribution Systems: Capacitors are used to provide reactive power compensation in distribution networks to reduce power losses and to maintain a voltage profile within acceptable limits. The ultimate goal for optimal capacitor placement problem in radial distribution system is to investigate the best location and size of shunt capacitors to maximize loss reduction and to minimize the total cost. In the presence of non linear loads, more harmonics are being injected into distribution systems. The addition of shunt capacitors may lead to high distortion levels causing damage to the electric equipment. As a result, shunt capacitors

